

THE IMPORTANCE OF THINKING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL COGNITIVE PROCESSES IN CHILDREN

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Annotatsiya; The article talks about the development of thinking in children and its influence on children's psychology.

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Thinking is not gifted to a person at a certain age or period. He comes to the world together with the child when he is born. Later, it develops and becomes complicated together with the child. The concept of thinking in young children is a little more colorful than in an adult. That is, they have a wide range of fantasy, concepts are based on slight exaggerations rather than real events. All these are the products of thinking. If we explain the concept of thinking from a scientific point of view, only theoretical information is needed. Children look at the world differently until they reach adolescence. That is, the processes of analysis and synthesis are easier for them in some aspects, and understanding some aspects is more difficult. Children should be helped by their parents in understanding the world. It is unlikely that this work will be carried out effectively, especially by the mother. Because mother's role in child education is bigger than father's. The events that took place around are shown in the children's thinking in a visual-image form. They do not remember an event or a person through unfamiliar words, but on the basis of embodying it in front of their eyes. Young children have more images than reasoning.

The importance of the concept of thinking in children's minds

In their thinking, the word becomes a secondary tool. For example, Professor B.C. Mukhina; He said that it is easier for children to explain through actions than to explain in words. That is, if you give them a broken toy for repair, they will only show you the repair process.

They have some difficulty when it comes to speaking. But in 5-year-old children, the wealth of speech grows rapidly. Curiosity develops as well. We should learn this from the various questions they ask us. We should not forget that we should try to answer the questions asked by children as correctly as possible. Because as a result of unanswered questions, children's interest begins to wane. Parents are responsible for the development of children's thinking. Various useful games, health exercises, and proper analysis of the surrounding events, as well

as telling various fairy tales and instructive stories to enliven images in their thinking, greatly contribute to the development of thinking in children's minds. We should teach children not only the white side of life, but sometimes the black side, that is, some truths, and at the same time, we should explain that the world around them is not only black and white, but consists of various colors.

Along with the concept of thinking, children also have the concepts of intelligence and creativity. They always go hand in hand. The reason is that these concepts are interrelated. Sometimes we can see such children whose level of thinking and thinking makes even some older people in a hurry. It is in them that mental processes are well developed. Intellect is perceiving, remembering, thinking, talking with people, and similar situations. Not only the family, but also the society contributes to the development of such concepts in children. But such intelligences are formed differently in children, some have a higher level, some have a lower level. Creativity is the same, if five children are given green plasticine, they will make the objects of their imagination from this color. That is, they put into practice what is green in their thinking. Creativity and intelligence do not develop like this in children. Heredity and genealogy also depend on its appearance. If one of the parents or relatives has high creativity or mental processes, their children will grow up to be mentally and physically well-rounded individuals. Because it is precisely these concepts that will develop them in their later adulthood.

Different scholars have expressed different opinions about thinking. For example, according to the German philosopher Martin Heidegger, the main feature of the existence of thinking is imagination. According to the philosopher, thinking exists because people are imagining. I think no one can deny this idea. Because as a result of thoughts, imaginations arise. This situation is more interesting for young children than for adults. It is through these imaginations that children embody the heroes of fairy tales told by their grandmothers. After the processes of analysis and synthesis of the good or bad qualities of the heroes of the fairy tale, a conclusion of the general imagination is formed. Parents should be careful in shaping their children's imaginations. A single action or event creates black spots in children's imaginations. In addition, in society, we hear sentences about children, "Sit quietly, don't interfere too much, you already know something." In fact, these statements are wrong. The famous German writer Romain Rolland said: a man is a triple murderer." We should also be careful.

Let's not become killers of children's thinking...

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